

On Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Hyperbolic Functions

Ahmad A. Abubaker¹, Nedal Tahat², Sara A. Khalil³, Khaled Matarneh⁴, Mutaz Shatnawi⁵, Ahmed Atallah Alsaraireh⁶, P. Prabakaran⁷ and Abdallah Al-Husban^{8,9,*}

¹Faculty of Computer Studies, Arab Open University, Saudi Arabia; a.abubaker@arabou.edu.sa

²Department of Mathematics, Faculty of science, The Hashemite University, P. O. Box 330127, Zarqa, 13133, Jordan; nedal@hu.edu.jo

³Mathematics Department, Faculty of Science, Applied Science Private University (ASU) Amman, Jordan; s_khalil@asu.edu.jo

⁴Faculty of Computer Studies, Arab Open University, Saudi Arabia; k.matarneh@arabou.edu.sa

⁵Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Technology, Irbid National University, Irbid 21110, Jordan; m.shatnawi@inu.edu.jo

⁶The university of Jordan –Aqaba Department of computer information systems; a.alsarairah@ju.edu.jo

⁷Department of Mathematics, Bannari Amman Institute of Technology, Erode - 638401, Tamil Nadu, India; prabakaranpvkr@gmail.com

⁸Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Technology, Irbid National University, Irbid 21110, Jordan; dralhosban@inu.edu.jo

⁹Jadara Research Center, Jadara University, Irbid 21110, Jordan

*Correspondence: dralhosban@inu.edu.jo

Abstract. In this article, we have introduced and studied the concept of symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic functions and the symbolic 2-plithogenic identities. Also, we have discussed the derivatives and integrals of the symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic functions and presented the logarithmic forms of the inverse symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic functions.

Keywords: Symbolic 2-plithogenic function; hyperbolic fraction; symbolic 2-plithogenic derivatives and symbolic 2-plithogenic integrals.

1. Introduction

The concept of refined neutrosophic structure was studied by many authors in [1–4]. Symbolic plithogenic algebraic structures are introduced by Smarandache, that are very similar to refined neutrosophic structures with some differences in the definition of the multiplication operation [11].

In [10], the algebraic properties of symbolic 2-plithogenic rings generated from the fusion of symbolic plithogenic sets with algebraic rings are studied. In [12,13] was studied the concepts of symbolic 2-plithogenic vector spaces and modules.

Recent works have significantly advanced the theoretical and applied aspects of fuzzy and neutrosophic structures, including the development of various neutrosophic ideals in ternary semigroups [14], the exploration of intuitionistic and fuzzy algebraic systems [15, 19, 22], novel weighted and trigonometric operators in complex fuzzy environments [16, 17], and the integration of neutrosophic models in graph theory and numerical analysis [20, 21, 26, 27]; these efforts are further extended by applications in intelligent systems, health technologies, and topological frameworks [18, 23–25].

In [6], Alhasan Yaser et al., presented the concept of the symbolic plithogenic differentials calculus, where the symbolic plithogenic differentiable is defined. Also in [7], they discussed integrations in symbolic plithogenic field, where they presented direct methods for solving integrations of symbolic plithogenic functions. Further the indefinite plithogenic trigonometric integrals was discussed in [8].

Recently, in [5], Alhasan Yaser et al., introduced the idea of the neutrosophic hyperbolic functions and studied the derivatives and integrals of the neutrosophic hyperbolic functions and inverse neutrosophic hyperbolic functions. As an extension, in [9], the concept of 2-refined neutrosophic hyperbolic functions with its differential and integrals was introduced and studied.

Motivated by these works, we introduced the concept of symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic functions, the symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic identities in this article. Also, we have studied derivatives and integrals of the symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic functions and presented the logarithmic forms of the inverse symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic functions.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [10] Let R be a ring, the symbolic 2-plithogenic ring is defined as follows:

$$2 - SP_R = \left\{ a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2; a_i \in R, P_j^2 = P_j, P_1 \times P_2 = P_{\max(1,2)} = P_2 \right\}$$

Smarandache has defined algebraic operations on $2 - SP_R$ as follows:

Addition:

$$[a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2] + [b_0 + b_1P_1 + b_2P_2] = (a_0 + b_0) + (a_1 + b_1)P_1 + (a_2 + b_2)P_2$$

Multiplication:

$$[a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2] \cdot [b_0 + b_1P_1 + b_2P_2] = a_0b_0 + a_0b_1P_1 + a_0b_2P_2 + a_1b_0P_1^2 + a_1b_2P_1P_2 + a_2b_0P_2 + a_2b_1P_1P_2 + a_2b_2P_2^2 + a_1b_1P_1P_1 = (a_0b_0) + (a_0b_1 + a_1b_0 + a_1b_1)P_1 + (a_0b_2 + a_1b_2 + a_2b_0 + a_2b_1 + a_2b_2)P_2.$$

It is clear that $2 - SP_R$ is a ring. If R is a field, then $2 - SP_R$ is called a symbolic 2-plithogenic

field. Also, if R is commutative, then $2 - SP_R$ is commutative, and if R has a unity (1), then $2 - SP_R$ has the same unity (1).

Definition 2.2. [6] The rules of the symbolic plithogenic derivatives

Let $PN_r = a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2 + \dots + a_rP_r$ and $PN_s = b_0 + b_1P_1 + b_2P_2 + \dots + b_sP_s \in SPS$ then we can prove each of the following:

- (1) $\frac{d}{dx}[PC] = 0$; where $PN = c_0 + c_1P_1 + c_2P_2 + \dots + c_rP_r$ is symbolic plithogenic constant.
- (2) $\frac{d}{dx}[PN_sx + PN_r] = PN_s$
- (3) $\frac{d}{dx}[PN_sx^n] = nPN_sx^{n-1}$; n is real number.
- (4) $\frac{d}{dx}[e^{PN_sx+PN_r}] = PN_s e^{PN_sx+PN_r}$

Definition 2.3. [7] Let $f : SPS \rightarrow SPS$ to evaluate $\int f(x, PN)dx$, where $PN = d_0 + d_1P_1 + d_2P_2 + \dots + d_nP_n$, put : $x = g(u) \Rightarrow dx = g'(u)du$, by substitution we get

$$\int f(x, PN)dx = \int f(u)g'(u)du$$

then we can directly integral it.

Theorem 2.4. [7] If $\int f(x, PN)dx = \varphi(x, PN)$, then:

$$\int PN_r f(PN_sx + PN_n)dx = \frac{PN_r}{PN_s} \varphi(PN_sx + PN_n) + PC$$

provided that $\frac{PN_r}{PN_s}$ is divisible, where $PN_r = a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2 + \dots + a_rP_r$ and $PN_n = c_0 + c_1P_1 + c_2P_2 + \dots + c_rP_r \in SPS$ is symbolic plithogenic constant.

3. Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Hyperbolic Functions

Let $f(x, P_1, P_2) = e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}$, then we can express the symbolic 2-plithogenic function as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x, P_1, P_2) &= e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} \\ &= \frac{e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} + e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}}{2} \\ &\quad + \frac{e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} - e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}}{2} \end{aligned}$$

The odd function is called the symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic sine function of x and the even function is called the symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic cosine function of x .

Hence for all $x \in (-\infty, +\infty)$

$$\sinh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$= \frac{e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} - e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}}{2}$$

$$\cosh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$= \frac{e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} + e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}}{2}$$

where $a_1, b_1, c_1, a_2, b_2, c_2$ are real numbers.

Now, let us write the definition of symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic functions as follows:

Definition 3.1. The symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic sine function of x is

$$\begin{aligned} \sinh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\ = \frac{e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} - e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}}{2} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.2. The symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic cosine function of x is

$$\begin{aligned} \cosh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\ = \frac{e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} + e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}}{2} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.3. The symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic tangent function of x is

$$\begin{aligned} \tanh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\ = \frac{e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} - e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}}{e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} + e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.4. The symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic cotangent function of x is

$$\begin{aligned} \coth((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\ = \frac{e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} + e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}}{e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} - e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.5. The symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic secant function of x is

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{sech}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\ = \frac{1}{\cosh((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} \\ = \frac{2}{e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} + e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.6. The symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic cosecant function of x is

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{cosech}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\ = \frac{1}{\sinh((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} \\ = \frac{2}{e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} - e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}} \end{aligned}$$

4. Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Hyperbolic Identities

$$(1) \cosh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) + \sinh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= e^{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} \\
 (2) \quad & \cosh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) - \sinh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\
 &= e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))} \\
 (3) \quad & \cosh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) - \sinh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) = 1 \\
 (4) \quad & \operatorname{sech}^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) + \operatorname{tanh}^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) = 1 \\
 (5) \quad & \operatorname{coth}^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) - \operatorname{cosech}^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) = 1 \\
 (6) \quad & \sinh(2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))) \\
 &= \\
 (7) \quad & 2\sinh((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))\cosh((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2)) \\
 & \cosh(2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))) \\
 &= 2\sinh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) + 1 \\
 &= 2\cosh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) - 1 \\
 &= \cosh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\
 & \quad + \sinh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\
 (8) \quad & \sinh^2(2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))) = \frac{\cosh(2((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2)))-1}{2} \\
 (9) \quad & \cosh^2(2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))) = \frac{\cosh(2((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2)))+1}{2}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. It is easy to prove the symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic identities. For example let us see the proof of identity (7) and (5).

Proof of (7):

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \cosh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) + \sinh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\
 &= \left[\frac{e^{(a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2)} + e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}}{2} \right]^2 \\
 & \quad + \left[\frac{e^{(a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2)} - e^{-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}}{2} \right]^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{2e^{2((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}+2e^{-2((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}}{4} \\
 &= \frac{e^{2((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}+e^{-2((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))}}{2} \\
 &= \cosh(2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

Moreover,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\cosh(2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))) \\
 &= \cosh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\
 &\quad + \sinh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\
 &= 1 + \sinh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\
 &\quad + \sinh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\
 &= 1 + 2\sinh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))
 \end{aligned}$$

And,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\cosh(2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))) \\
 &= \cosh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\
 &\quad + \sinh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\
 &= \cosh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) \\
 &\quad + \cosh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) - 1 \\
 &= 2\cosh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) - 1
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof of (5):

$$\cosh^2((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))-\sinh^2((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2)) = 1$$

Divide both sides by $\sinh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$

$$\frac{\cosh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))}{\sinh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))} - 1 = \frac{1}{\sinh^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))}$$

$$\coth^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) = 1 + \operatorname{cosech}^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$\coth^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) - \operatorname{cosech}^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) = 1 \square$$

5. Derivatives of Symbolic 2-Plithogenic hyperbolic functions

$$(1) \frac{d}{dx}[\sinh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))]$$

$$= (a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)\cosh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$(2) \frac{d}{dx}[\cosh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))]$$

$$= (a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)\sinh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$(3) \frac{d}{dx}[\tanh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))]$$

$$= (a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)\operatorname{sech}^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$(4) \frac{d}{dx}[\coth((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))]$$

$$= -(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)\operatorname{cosech}^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$(5) \frac{d}{dx}[\operatorname{sech}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))]$$

$$= -(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)\operatorname{sech}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$\tanh((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$(6) \frac{d}{dx}[\operatorname{cosech}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))]$$

$$= -(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)\operatorname{cosech}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$\coth((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

Example 5.1.

$$(1) \frac{d}{dx}[\sinh((3 + 6P_1 + P_2)x^3 + (5 + 7P_1 + 6P_2))]$$

$$= 3(3 + 6P_1 + P_2)x^2\cosh((3 + 6P_1 + P_2)x^3 + (5 + 7P_1 + 6P_2))$$

$$(2) \frac{d}{dx}[\cosh(2((-1 - P_1 - 5P_2)x + (3P_1 + P_2)))]$$

$$= \frac{d}{dx}[2\cosh^2((-1 - P_1 - 5P_2)x + (3P_1 + P_2)) - 1]$$

$$= -4(1 + P_1 + 5P_2)\cosh((-1 - P_1 - 5P_2)x + (3P_1 + P_2))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sinh((-1 - P_1 - 5P_2)x + (3P_1 + P_2)) \\
 (3) \quad & \frac{d}{dx}[\cosh^2((5 - 3P_1 - 2P_2)x + (-2 - P_1 + P_2))] \\
 & = \frac{d}{dx}[\frac{\cosh(2((5-3P_1-2P_2)x+(-2-P_1+P_2)))+1}{2}] \\
 & = (5 - 3P_1 - 2P_2)\sinh(2((5 - 3P_1 - 2P_2)x + (-2 - P_1 + P_2))) \\
 (4) \quad & \frac{d}{dx}[\coth((1 - 4P_1)x + (-4 + 7P_1 + 9P_2))] \\
 & = (-1 + 4P_1)\operatorname{cosech}^2((1 - 4P_1)x + (-4 + 7P_1 + 9P_2)) \\
 (5) \quad & \frac{d}{dx}[\tanh\sqrt{((1 + P_1 + 2P_2)^2x^2 + P_1 - P_2)}] \\
 & = \frac{2(1+P_1+2P_2)^2x\operatorname{sech}^2\sqrt{((1+P_1+2P_2)^2x^2+P_1-P_2)}}{2\sqrt{((1+P_1+2P_2)^2x^2+P_1-P_2)}} \\
 & = \frac{(1+P_1^2+4P_2^2+2P_1+4P_1P_2+4P_2)x\operatorname{sech}^2\sqrt{((1+P_1+2P_2)^2x^2+P_1-P_2)}}{\sqrt{((1+P_1+2P_2)^2x^2+P_1-P_2)}} \\
 & = \frac{(1+3P_1+12P_2)x\operatorname{sech}^2\sqrt{((1+P_1+2P_2)^2x^2+P_1-P_2)}}{\sqrt{((1+P_1+2P_2)^2x^2+P_1-P_2)}}
 \end{aligned}$$

6. Derivatives of Inverse Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Hyperbolic Functions

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad & \frac{d}{dx}[\sinh^{-1}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))] = \\
 & \frac{(a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)}{\sqrt{1+((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))^2}}. \\
 (2) \quad & \frac{d}{dx}[\cosh^{-1}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))] = \\
 & \frac{(a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)}{\sqrt{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))^2-1}}; \\
 & x > \frac{1-a_2-b_2P_1-c_2P_2}{a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2}. \\
 (3) \quad & \frac{d}{dx}[\tanh^{-1}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))] = \\
 & \frac{(a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)}{1-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))^2}; \\
 & |(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)| < 1. \\
 (4) \quad & \frac{d}{dx}[\coth^{-1}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))] = \\
 & \frac{(a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)}{1-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))^2}; \\
 & |(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)| > 1. \\
 (5) \quad & \frac{d}{dx}[\operatorname{sech}^{-1}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))] \\
 & = \frac{(-a_1-b_1P_1-c_1P_2)}{((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))\sqrt{1-((a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)x+(a_2+b_2P_1+c_2P_2))^2}}; \\
 & \frac{-a_2-b_2P_1-c_2P_2}{a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2} < x < \frac{1-a_2-b_2P_1-c_2P_2}{a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2} \\
 (6) \quad & \frac{d}{dx}[\operatorname{cosech}^{-1}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{(-a_1 - b_1 P_1 - c_1 P_2)}{|((a_1 + b_1 P_1 + c_1 P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2 P_1 + c_2 P_2))| \sqrt{1 + ((a_1 + b_1 P_1 + c_1 P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2 P_1 + c_2 P_2))^2}}; x \neq \frac{-a_2 - b_2 P_1 - c_2 P_2}{a_1 + b_1 P_1 + c_1 P_2}$$

Example 6.1.

$$(1) \frac{d}{dx} [\sinh^{-1}((3 + P_1 - 2P_2)x + (P_1 + 5P_2))] = \frac{3 + P_1 - 2P_2}{\sqrt{1 + ((3 + P_1 - 2P_2)x + (P_1 + 5P_2))^2}}$$

$$(2) \frac{d}{dx} [\cosh^{-1}((2 + 3P_1 + 4P_2)x + (-1 - P_1 - P_2))] = \frac{2 + 3P_1 + 4P_2}{\sqrt{((2 + 3P_1 + 4P_2)x + (-1 - P_1 - P_2))^2 - 1}}$$

$$(3) \frac{d}{dx} [\coth^{-1}(\cos((5 + 6P_1 - 2P_2)x + (3P_1 - 4P_2)))]$$

$$= \frac{-(5 + 6P_1 - 2P_2)\sin((5 + 6P_1 - 2P_2)x + (3P_1 - 4P_2))}{1 - \cos^2((5 + 6P_1 - 2P_2)x + (3P_1 - 4P_2))}$$

$$= \frac{-(5 + 6P_1 - 2P_2)\sin((5 + 6P_1 - 2P_2)x + (3P_1 - 4P_2))}{\sin^2((5 + 6P_1 - 2P_2)x + (3P_1 - 4P_2))}$$

$$= \frac{-5 - 6P_1 + 2P_2}{\sin((5 + 6P_1 - 2P_2)x + (3P_1 - 4P_2))}$$

$$= (-5 - 6P_1 + 2P_2)\operatorname{cosec}((5 + 6P_1 - 2P_2)x + (3P_1 - 4P_2))$$

$$(4) \frac{d}{dx} [(4 + P_1 + P_2)x \sinh^{-1}((P_1 + P_2)x + (2 + P_1 - 7P_2))]$$

$$= (4 + P_1 + P_2) \sinh^{-1}((P_1 + P_2)x + (2 + P_1 - 7P_2)) + (4 + P_1 + P_2)x \frac{P_1 + P_2}{\sqrt{1 + ((P_1 + P_2)x + (2 + P_1 - 7P_2))^2}}$$

$$= (4 + P_1 + P_2) [\sinh^{-1}((P_1 + P_2)x + (2 + P_1 - 7P_2)) + \frac{(P_1 + P_2)x}{\sqrt{1 + ((P_1 + P_2)x + (2 + P_1 - 7P_2))^2}}]$$

$$(5) \frac{d}{dx} [\operatorname{cosech}^{-1}((8 + 9P_1 + 7P_2)x + (1 - 3P_1 + 11P_2))]$$

$$= \frac{-(8 + 9P_1 + 7P_2)}{|(8 + 9P_1 + 7P_2)x + (1 - 3P_1 + 11P_2)| \sqrt{1 + ((8 + 9P_1 + 7P_2)x + (1 - 3P_1 + 11P_2))^2}}$$

7. Integrals of Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Hyperbolic Functions

Let $a_1 \neq 0, a_1 \neq -b_1, a_1 + b_1 + c_1 \neq 0$ and $a_1, b_1, c_1, a_2, b_2, c_2$ are real numbers, while P_1, P_2 are indeterminacy. Then

$$(1) \int \sinh((a_1 + b_1 P_1 + c_1 P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2 P_1 + c_2 P_2)) dx$$

$$= (\frac{1}{a_1} - \frac{b_1}{a_1(a_1 + b_1)} P_1 - \frac{c_1}{(a_1 + b_1)(a_1 + b_1 + c_1)} P_2) \cosh((a_1 + b_1 P_1 + c_1 P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2 P_1 + c_2 P_2)) + C$$

$$(2) \int \cosh((a_1 + b_1 P_1 + c_1 P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2 P_1 + c_2 P_2)) dx$$

$$= (\frac{1}{a_1} - \frac{b_1}{a_1(a_1 + b_1)} P_1 - \frac{c_1}{(a_1 + b_1)(a_1 + b_1 + c_1)} P_2) \sinh((a_1 + b_1 P_1 + c_1 P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2 P_1 + c_2 P_2)) + C$$

$$(3) \int \operatorname{sech}^2((a_1 + b_1 P_1 + c_1 P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2 P_1 + c_2 P_2)) dx$$

$$= (\frac{1}{a_1} - \frac{b_1}{a_1(a_1 + b_1)} P_1 - \frac{c_1}{(a_1 + b_1)(a_1 + b_1 + c_1)} P_2) \tanh((a_1 + b_1 P_1 + c_1 P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2 P_1 + c_2 P_2)) + C$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(4) \quad & \int \operatorname{cosech}^2((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))dx \\
& = \\
& -\left(\frac{1}{a_1} - \frac{b_1}{a_1(a_1+b_1)}P_1 - \frac{c_1}{(a_1+b_1)(a_1+b_1+c_1)}P_2\right)\operatorname{coth}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) + C \\
(5) \quad & \int \operatorname{sech}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))\operatorname{tanh}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))dx \\
& = \\
& -\left(\frac{1}{a_1} - \frac{b_1}{a_1(a_1+b_1)}P_1 - \frac{c_1}{(a_1+b_1)(a_1+b_1+c_1)}P_2\right)\operatorname{sech}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) + C \\
(6) \quad & \int \operatorname{cosech}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))\operatorname{coth}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))dx \\
& = -\left(\frac{1}{a_1} - \frac{b_1}{a_1(a_1+b_1)}P_1 - \frac{c_1}{(a_1+b_1)(a_1+b_1+c_1)}P_2\right)\operatorname{cosech}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + \\
& b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) + C
\end{aligned}$$

where $C = a_0 + b_0P_1 + c_0P_2$ is integration constant and a_0, b_0, c_0 are real numbers.

Example 7.1.

$$\begin{aligned}
(1) \quad & \int \cosh((4 + P_1 + P_2)x + (2 + P_1 - 7P_2))dx \\
& = \left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{20}P_1 - \frac{1}{30}P_2\right)\sinh((4 + P_1 + P_2)x + (2 + P_1 - 7P_2)) + C \\
(2) \quad & \int \sinh^2((3 + P_1 - 2P_2)x + (1 + P_1 + P_2))dx \\
& = \int \frac{\cosh(2((3+P_1-2P_2)x+(1+P_1+P_2)))-1}{2} dx \\
& = \int \frac{\cosh((6+2P_1-4P_2)x+(2+2P_1+2P_2))-1}{2} dx \\
& = \left(\frac{1}{12} - \frac{1}{48}P_1 + \frac{1}{16}P_2\right)\sinh((4 + P_1 + P_2)x + (2 + P_1 - 7P_2)) - \frac{x}{2} + C \\
(3) \quad & \int \tanh((4 - 2P_1 + P_2)x + (2 - 3P_1 - 5P_2))dx \\
& = \int \frac{\sinh((4-2P_1+P_2)x+(2-3P_1-5P_2))}{\cosh((4-2P_1+P_2)x+(2-3P_1-5P_2))} dx \\
& \text{Put} \\
& u = \cosh((4 - 2P_1 + P_2)x + (2 - 3P_1 - 5P_2)) \\
& \Rightarrow du = (4 - 2P_1 + P_2)\sinh((4 - 2P_1 + P_2)x + (2 - 3P_1 - 5P_2))dx \\
& \Rightarrow \frac{du}{4-2P_1+P_2} = \sinh((4 - 2P_1 + P_2)x + (2 - 3P_1 - 5P_2))dx \\
& \int \tanh((4 - 2P_1 + P_2)x + (2 - 3P_1 - 5P_2))dx \\
& = \frac{1}{4-2P_1+P_2} \int \frac{du}{u} \\
& = \frac{1}{4-2P_1+P_2} \ln|u| + C \\
& = \frac{1}{4-2P_1+P_2} \ln|\cosh((4 - 2P_1 + P_2)x + (2 - 3P_1 - 5P_2))| + C \\
& = \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{4}P_1 - \frac{1}{6}P_2\right)\ln|\cosh((4 - 2P_1 + P_2)x + (2 - 3P_1 - 5P_2))| + C \\
(4) \quad & \int \sinh^3((3 + 5P_1 + 7P_2)x - 11P_1 + 13P_2)\cosh((3 + 5P_1 + 7P_2)x - 11P_1 + 13P_2))dx
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Put } u = \sinh((3 + 5P_1 + 7P_2)x - 11P_1 + 13P_2))$$

$$\Rightarrow du = (3 + 5P_1 + 7P_2)\cosh((3 + 5P_1 + 7P_2)x - 11P_1 + 13P_2))dx$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{du}{3+5P_1+7P_2} = \cosh((3 + 5P_1 + 7P_2)x - 11P_1 + 13P_2))dx$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} & \int \sinh^3((3 + 5P_1 + 7P_2)x - 11P_1 + 13P_2))\cosh((3 + 5P_1 + 7P_2)x - 11P_1 + 13P_2))dx \\ &= \frac{1}{3+5P_1+7P_2} \int u^3 du \\ &= \frac{1}{3+5P_1+7P_2} \frac{u^4}{4} + C \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{3} - \frac{5}{24}P_1 - \frac{7}{120}P_2\right) \frac{\sinh^4((3+5P_1+7P_2)x-11P_1+13P_2))}{4} + C \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{12} - \frac{5}{96}P_1 - \frac{7}{480}P_2\right) \sinh^4((3 + 5P_1 + 7P_2)x - 11P_1 + 13P_2)) + C \\ (5) & \int [(4 + 5P_1 + 6P_2)x + (5 - P_1 - P_2)]\cosh[((4 + 5P_1 + 6P_2)x + (5 - P_1 - P_2))^2]dx \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Put } u = ((4 + 5P_1 + 6P_2)x + (5 - P_1 - P_2))^2$$

$$\Rightarrow du = 2(4 + 5P_1 + 6P_2)((4 + 5P_1 + 6P_2)x + (5 - P_1 - P_2))dx$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{du}{2(4+5P_1+6P_2)} = [(4 + 5P_1 + 6P_2)x + (5 - P_1 - P_2)]dx$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} & \int [(4 + 5P_1 + 6P_2)x + (5 - P_1 - P_2)]\cosh[((4 + 5P_1 + 6P_2)x + (5 - P_1 - P_2))^2]dx \\ &= \frac{1}{2(4+5P_1+6P_2)} \int \cosh u du \\ &= \frac{1}{2(4+5P_1+6P_2)} \sinh u + C \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{8} - \frac{5}{72}P_1 - \frac{1}{45}P_2\right) \sinh[((4 + 5P_1 + 6P_2)x + (5 - P_1 - P_2))^2] + C \end{aligned}$$

8. Logarithmic forms of inverse Symbolic 2-Plithogenic hyperbolic functions

$$(1) \sinh^{-1}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \ln[(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2) + \\ & \sqrt{((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))^2 + 1}] \end{aligned}$$

$$|(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)| < \infty$$

$$(2) \cosh^{-1}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$= \ln\left[\frac{(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2) + \sqrt{((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))^2 - 1}}{2}\right]$$

$$x \geq \frac{1 - (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)}{a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2}$$

$$(3) \tanh^{-1}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{1 + (a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)}{1 - (a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x - (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)}\right); |(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)| < 1$$

$$(4) \coth^{-1}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2) + 1}{(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2) - 1}\right); |(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)| > 1$$

$$(5) \operatorname{sech}^{-1}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) =$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{1 - ((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))^2}}{(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)}\right);$$

$$0 < ((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) < 1$$

$$(6) \operatorname{cosech}^{-1}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$= \ln\left(\frac{1}{(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)} + \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 - ((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))^2}}{|(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)|}\right); x \neq -\frac{a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2}{a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2}$$

Proof. For example let us see the proof of the result (3).

$$\text{Let } u = \tanh^{-1}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2))$$

$$(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2) = \tanh u = \frac{e^u - e^{-u}}{e^u + e^{-u}}$$

$$\frac{1 + \frac{e^u - e^{-u}}{e^u + e^{-u}}}{1 - \frac{e^u - e^{-u}}{e^u + e^{-u}}} = \frac{1 + (a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)}{1 - (a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x - (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)}$$

$$e^{2u} = \frac{1 + (a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)}{1 - (a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x - (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)}$$

Taking log on both sides we get

$$u = \frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{1 + (a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)}{1 - (a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x - (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)}\right)$$

$$\tanh^{-1}((a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)) = \frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{1 + (a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x + (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)}{1 - (a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)x - (a_2 + b_2P_1 + c_2P_2)}\right)$$

□

9. Integrals of inverse Symbolic 2-Plithogenic hyperbolic functions

$$(1) \int \frac{1}{\sqrt{(a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)^2+x^2}} dx = \sinh^{-1}\left(\frac{x}{a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2}\right) + C = \ln(x + \sqrt{(a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)^2 + x^2}) + C$$

$$(2) \int \frac{1}{\sqrt{x^2-(a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)^2}} dx = \cosh^{-1}\left(\frac{x}{a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2}\right) + C$$

$$= \ln(x + \sqrt{x^2 - (a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2)^2}) + C; x > a_1 + b_1P_1 + c_1P_2$$

$$(3) \int \frac{1}{(a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)^2-x^2} dx$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{a_1} - \frac{b_1}{a_1(a_1+b_1)}P_1 - \frac{c_1}{(a_1+b_1)(a_1+b_1+c_1)}P_2\right) \tanh^{-1}\left(\frac{x}{a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2}\right) + C$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{a_1} - \frac{b_1}{a_1(a_1+b_1)}P_1 - \frac{c_1}{(a_1+b_1)(a_1+b_1+c_1)}P_2\right) \coth^{-1}\left(\frac{x}{a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2}\right) + C$$

$$= \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{a_1} - \frac{b_1}{a_1(a_1+b_1)}P_1 - \frac{c_1}{(a_1+b_1)(a_1+b_1+c_1)}P_2\right) \ln\left|\frac{a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2+x}{a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2-x}\right| + C$$

$$(4) \int \frac{1}{x\sqrt{(a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)^2-x^2}} dx$$

$$= -\left(\frac{1}{a_1} - \frac{b_1}{a_1(a_1+b_1)}P_1 - \frac{c_1}{(a_1+b_1)(a_1+b_1+c_1)}P_2\right) \operatorname{sech}^{-1}\left|\frac{x}{a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2}\right| + C$$

$$= -\left(\frac{1}{a_1} - \frac{b_1}{a_1(a_1+b_1)}P_1 - \frac{c_1}{(a_1+b_1)(a_1+b_1+c_1)}P_2\right) \ln\left(\frac{a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2+\sqrt{(a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)^2-x^2}}{|x|}\right) + C$$

$$(5) \int \frac{1}{x\sqrt{(a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)^2+x^2}} dx$$

$$= -\left(\frac{1}{a_1} - \frac{b_1}{a_1(a_1+b_1)}P_1 - \frac{c_1}{(a_1+b_1)(a_1+b_1+c_1)}P_2\right) \operatorname{cosech}^{-1}\left|\frac{x}{a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2}\right| + C$$

$$= -\left(\frac{1}{a_1} - \frac{b_1}{a_1(a_1+b_1)}P_1 - \frac{c_1}{(a_1+b_1)(a_1+b_1+c_1)}P_2\right) \ln\left(\frac{a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2+\sqrt{(a_1+b_1P_1+c_1P_2)^2+x^2}}{|x|}\right) + C; x \neq 0$$

Example 9.1.

$$(1) \int \frac{1}{\sqrt{(3+5P_1-2P_2)^2+x^2}} dx = \sinh^{-1}\left[\frac{x}{3+5P_1-2P_2}\right] + C = \sinh^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{3} - \frac{5}{24}P_1 + \frac{1}{24}P_2\right)x + C$$

(or)

$$\int \frac{1}{\sqrt{(3+5P_1-2P_2)^2+x^2}} dx$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \ln(x + \sqrt{(3 + 5P_1 - 2P_2)^2 + x^2}) + C \\
 &= \ln(x + \sqrt{9 + 25P_1^2 + 4P_2^2 + 30P_1 - 20P_1P_2 - 12P_2 + x^2}) + C \\
 &= \ln(x + \sqrt{9 + 25P_1 + 4P_2 + 30P_1 - 20P_2 - 12P_2 + x^2}) + C \\
 &= \ln(x + \sqrt{9 + 55P_1 - 28P_2 + x^2}) + C \\
 (2) \int \frac{e^{(5+P_2)x}}{(-2+P_1-3P_2)^2 - e^{2(5+P_2)x}} dx \\
 \text{Let } u = e^{(5+P_2)x} \Rightarrow du = (5 + P_2)e^{(5+P_2)x} dx \Rightarrow \frac{du}{5+P_2} = e^{(5+P_2)x} dx \\
 \int \frac{e^{(5+P_2)x}}{(-2+P_1-3P_2)^2 - e^{2(5+P_2)x}} dx \\
 &= \frac{1}{5+P_2} \int \frac{1}{(-2+P_1-3P_2)^2 - u^2} du \\
 &= \frac{1}{5+P_2} \left[\frac{1}{-2+P_1-3P_2} \tanh^{-1}\left(\frac{u}{-2+P_1-3P_2}\right) \right] + C \\
 &= \frac{1}{(5+P_2)(-2+P_1-3P_2)} \tanh^{-1}\left(\frac{u}{-2+P_1-3P_2}\right) + C \\
 &= \frac{1}{-10+5P_1-19P_2} \tanh^{-1}\left(\frac{u}{-2+P_1-3P_2}\right) + C \\
 &= \left(-\frac{1}{10} - \frac{1}{10}P_1 + \frac{19}{120}P_2\right) \tanh^{-1}\left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{3}{4}P_2\right)u + C \\
 &= \left(-\frac{1}{10} - \frac{1}{10}P_1 + \frac{19}{120}P_2\right) \tanh^{-1}\left(\left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{3}{4}P_2\right)e^{(5+P_2)x}\right) + C
 \end{aligned}$$

10. Conclusions

This article is an extensio of the studies on symbolic 2-plithogenic derivatives and integrals. In this article we have introduced the concept of symbolic 2-plithogenic hyperbolic functions and symbolic 2-plithogenic inverse hyperbolic functions with its differential and integrals.

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